

The Photolytic Decomposition of Methyl Chloride

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The photolysis of methyl chloride in the vapour phase with 1849 Å line of Hg as the exciting radiation was carried out at three different temperatures. Methyl radical generated from the photolytic decomposition abstracts hydrogen atoms from the substrate molecules. Besides, methane, other major products are tetrachloroethane, hydrogen chloride and two other minor products. The photolysis was carried out in presence of hydrogen and nitrogen. Observations indicate that the initial step of photodissociation is carbon-chlorine bond cleavage. Quantum yield of these photo reactions were determined using purified ammonia as the chemical actinometer.

THE electronic absorption band of alkyl halides nearest the visible range occurs in the ultraviolet region and this has been attributed to the transition of non-bonding *p* electrons of halogen atoms¹. The absorption spectra of methyl chloride in the ultraviolet region was studied by Ysubomura *et al.*². This absorption band is continuous and therefore the excited molecule may dissociate to form radicals. Of the halomethanes methyl iodide has received the most attention for the photolytic dissociation³⁻¹⁰. Photolytic decomposition of chloroform was studied by Hill¹¹, and from the same study Semeluk and Unger^{12,13} concluded that the primary step of photodissociation of chloroform is the carbon-chlorine bond cleavage. In the case of methylene chloride similar observations were made¹⁴. The thermal decomposition of methyl chloride where molecules dissociate in the ground electronic energy level has been reported by several workers¹⁵⁻¹⁷. It was of interest to investigate the photodissociation of methyl chloride and to establish the primary step involved in this reaction.

Experimental

In the photochemical studies the reactant must be free from oxygen. A conventional high vacuum system (mercury free) was used giving 5.10^{-7} mm of Hg measured by means of a cold cathode supplied by H. S. Martin & Sons. The photolysis was carried out in a cylindrical quartz cell (5.0 cm in length, 2.5 cm in diameter) having two flat circular windows fused to the cell. Windows were made of Suprasil (synthetic quartz) manufactured by Engelhardt Industries. Suprasil is transparent in the vacuum ultraviolet down to 1650 Å. The cell could be isolated from the vacuum line and the high vacuum stopcock with silicone grease by the use of break seal. The lamp was a Custom made Hanovia low-pressure arc, adjusted for optimum emission at 1849 Å. Suprasil window was 2.5 cm in diameter. The lamp was tubular in shape with the dimension: length 70 cm and diameter 2.5 cm. The two electrodes were

located in the side arms parallel to each other and 62 cm apart. The window of the lamp had a tendency to collect mercury during operation. To prevent this, the lamp was heated near the window with a small piece of heating tape

Materials :

(a) Methyl chloride supplied by Matheson Coleman was purified by bulb to bulb distillation in vacuo. The distillation was carried out in a system consisting of three detachable traps. The first trap was kept immersed in a dewar filled with liquid air and the other two traps were kept immersed in ether slush. When sufficient quantity of methyl chloride was transferred to the third trap from the gas cylinder, it was detached, and methyl chloride was distilled off from the third to the second trap and from the second to the first trap. The methyl chloride was analysed gas chromatographically and was found to contain less than 0.005 mole percent impurities. (b) Anhydrous ammonia from C.I.R.A.R. was purified in the same way as described for methyl chloride. (c) Pharmaceutical hydrogen (Hg free) obtained from Linde Air Product Co. was passed over finely divided copper, the temperature of which was maintained at 425°-450°, to remove traces of oxygen. It was then passed through a phosphorous pentoxide drying tower in order to remove any traces of water. (d) Nitrogen was also obtained from the same firm and purified in the same manner as described for hydrogen. The light intensity was measured with a RCA935 photocell and a spot galvanometer. Temperature measurement was made through a chromel-alumel thermocouple attached along the cell wall. Pressure in the reaction vessel was measured with a spiral gauge which was calibrated against a barometer

After the photochemical reactions, the condensable products were collected in a U trap and non-condensable products were measured in a gas burette. It was then collected in a small ampoule with the help

of a toeppler pump and analysed in a gas chromatograph. The condensable products were collected in an ampoule which was kept immersed in liquid air and finally sealed off with a very small flame.

Most of the analysis was performed on a F & M Scientific Corporation gas chromatograph Model F & M 500. The column used for the analysis of the permanent gases was a two feet long molecular sieve 4A with nitrogen as the carrier gas. The chlorinated hydrocarbon products were analysed on a 10 feet column containing 10% silicon oil on 60/80 mesh chromosorb W, temperature programmed from 60° to 225° at a rate of 15°/min, with nitrogen carrier gas flow rate of 1 cc/sec. The hydrogen chloride was distilled into a trap containing sodium bicarbonate, and carbon dioxide produced was collected in a short ampoule. A 3 feet long silica gel column was used for the analysis. The data are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Actinometry :

Ammonia as the chemical actinometric substance in the region of 2000 Å has some advantages^{18,19}. Purification is easy and the products are hydrogen and nitrogen in the ratio of 3 : 1. It is transparent to 2537 Å irradiation but absorbs very strongly 1849 Å radiation. Wigg¹⁹ has calculated the quantum yield of ammonia decomposition at 1 atm. for a cell of the same geometry as the one used in the present investigation. The quantum yield calculated in the present study was based on this value.

Discussion

In order to arrive at the steps involved in the photoreaction a large number of experiments was

performed. In any photochemical reaction possibility of following steps should be considered in formulating the mechanism.

where σ is the surface activity factor, p is the total pressure of methyl chloride and foreign gas and d is the diameter of the cell. If reaction proceeds via molecular elimination, the following two steps will be important

The excited molecule if dissociates eliminating a molecule, will produce biradicals, $: \text{CHCl}$ or $: \text{CH}_2$ or both if dissociation (6) and (7) occur simultaneously.

TABLE 1. GAS PHASE PHOTOLYSIS OF METHYL CHLORIDE AT 7° WITH 1849 Å. IRRADIATION TIME 90 MIN. PRODUCT RATIO, QUANTUM YIELD BASED ON CH₃Cl DISAPPEARANCE

CH ₃ Cl pressure cm Hg	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	C ₂ H ₅ Cl	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂		Quantum yield
	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	CH ₄	CH ₄	
2.264	2.333	4.128	2.002	...	1.85	0.900	0.0298
4.58	3.052	5.582	2.621	...	1.83	0.855	0.0405
6.88	3.882	6.721	3.320	...	1.73	0.857	0.0492
9.32	4.928	9.031	4.531	0.014	1.83	0.920	0.0657
12.83	5.200	9.320	4.681	0.018	1.79	0.900	0.0682
16.32	5.281	9.328	4.732	0.022	1.76	0.895	0.0684
18.48	5.300	9.410	4.730	0.028	1.77	0.890	0.0689

TABLE 2. PHOTOLYSIS OF METHYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF HYDROGEN WITH 1849 Å. IRRADIATION TIME 90 MIN., TEMPERATURE 27°, METHYL CHLORIDE PRESSURE 2.264 CM HG, PRODUCT RATIOS, QUANTUM YIELD BASED ON CH₃Cl DISAPPEARANCE

Hydrogen pressure cm Hg	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	C ₂ H ₅ Cl	C ₂ H ₆	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂		Quantum yield
	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	moles.10 ⁶	CH ₄	CH ₄	
0	2.222	4.128	2.002	1.85	0.901	0.0298
10	2.021	1.821	1.813	0.801	0.461	0.901	0.898	0.0233
20	1.980	1.601	1.815	0.609	0.311	0.810	0.915	0.0200
30	1.710	1.470	1.731	0.588	0.276	0.860	1.010	0.0181
40	1.690	1.365	1.581	0.493	0.281	0.808	0.935	0.0170

TABLE 3. PHOTOLYSIS OF METHYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF NITROGEN WITH 1849 Å. IRRADIATION TIME 90 MIN., TEMPERATURE 27°, METHYL CHLORIDE PRESSURE 2.264 CM HG, PRODUCT RATIOS, QUANTUM YIELD BASED ON CH₃Cl DISAPPEARANCE

Nitrogen pressure cm Hg	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	C ₂ H ₅ Cl	C ₂ H ₆	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	Quantum yield
	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	CH ₄	CH ₄	
0	2.222	4.128	2.002	1.85	0.90	0.0298
10	1.183	2.183	0.840	0.81	0.46	1.84	0.71	0.0230
20	1.143	1.983	0.708	0.91	0.52	1.73	0.62	0.0226
30	0.851	1.451	0.609	0.98	0.55	1.70	0.72	0.0110
40	0.800	1.400	0.544	1.00	0.58	1.75	0.68	0.0191

TABLE 4. VARIATION OF PRODUCTS AND PRODUCT RATIOS WITH TEMPERATURE AND ADDED QUENCHING GAS. METHYL CHLORIDE PRESSURE 2.264 CM HG., IRRADIATION TIME 90 MIN.

Temp. (°C)	Nitrogen pressure cm Hg	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	C ₂ H ₅ Cl	C ₂ H ₆	C ₂ H ₄ Cl ₂	HCl	Quantum yield
		moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	moles.10 ⁸	CH ₄	CH ₄	
27	0	2.222	4.128	2.002	1.85	0.90	0.0298
27	30	0.851	4.458	1.511	0.981	0.550	1.70	0.77	0.0195
70	0	2.340	4.410	2.121	1.89	0.91	0.0318
70	30	2.282	4.374	2.232	0.641	0.414	1.92	0.97	0.0374
120	0	2.551	4.881	2.413	1.91	0.95	0.0351
120	30	2.331	4.621	2.334	0.743	0.488	1.98	1.00	0.0400

The recombination of similar radicals will produce C₂H₂Cl₂ or C₂H₄ or in case of occurrence of both (6) and (7), there is the possibility of formation of C₂H₃Cl by the recombination of dissimilar radicals. Moreover, hydrogen should be present in the products. None of these were detected in the product. The reaction of biradicals, :CH₂ and :CHCl₂, are fairly known^{20,21}. In the absence of C₂H₄ or C₂H₂Cl₂ or H₂ in the products, the possibility of molecular elimination is very small. Observations indicate that the photolysis of CH₃Cl proceeds through an initial carbon chlorine bond cleavage. Results of photolysis for varying CH₃Cl pressure is given in Table 1. At 2.264, 4.580 and 6.880 cm Hg methyl chloride pressure, CH₄, C₂H₄Cl₂ and HCl were identified and at 9.32 cm Hg and higher in addition to the above products, C₂H₅Cl was produced. The mechanism for small percentage conversion on photodissociation of methyl chloride via carbon chlorine bond cleavage may be described by adding a few more steps.

If the photodissociation proceeds as in (8), methyl radical will be in "hot" condition. H₃C... Cl bond energy per mole is 82 k.cal and 1849 Å is equivalent to 156 k.cal. Most of the excess energy,

(156-82) = 74 k.cal, will be carried by methyl radical and will abstract hydrogen atom from the substrate molecule as shown in (9). Cl atoms will also abstract hydrogen from methyl chloride. If (9) and (10) both are very fast then at steady state concentration it is expected that CH₄ and HCl will be in 1 : 1 ratio and CH₄ and C₂H₄Cl₂ will be in the ratio 2 : 1. Results shown in Table 1 support this view fairly well. Hydrogen chloride is always less than what it was expected as it was difficult to estimate hydrogen chloride. The procedure followed was to absorb HCl in NaHCO₃ and to collect the evolved CO₂ in an ampoule. CO₂ is also absorbed by NaHCO₃ to some extent and because of this, estimated hydrogen chloride is always slightly less.

The probability of the cleavage of carbon hydrogen bond of methyl chloride seems to be unlikely because of the absence of H₂ in the products. In order to prove this photolysis was performed in the presence of H₂. If (8) applies, then the following reactions will occur :

It is expected that k₁₄ will be greater than k₁₅. Therefore steady state concentration of CH₃ radicals will be higher than that of CH₂Cl radicals. Photolysis in the presence of H₂ will yield more CH₄ and therefore ratio of C₂H₄Cl₂ to CH₄ will be shifted in favour of CH₄ (Table 2).

Using the above approach one can write the rate of disappearance of CH_3Cl in terms of rate constants :

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\text{CH}_3\text{Cl}) = - \frac{2k_8 I_0}{k_2 + k_8 + k_3(\text{CH}_3\text{Cl}) + k_4(\text{M}) + k_5\sigma/pd} \quad \dots (16)$$

By definition the expression for the quantum yield is

$$= \frac{2k_8}{k_2 + k_8 + k_3(\text{CH}_3\text{Cl}) + k_4(\text{M}) + k_5\sigma/pd} \quad \dots (17)$$

Due to the presence of $k_5\sigma/pd$ factor the increase of pressure of CH_3Cl quantum yield will go up and this trend was observed (Table 1). The rate of increase of quantum yield decreases at higher pressure due to self quenching. This is also true, when the photolysis was carried out in presence of nitrogen (Table 3). If (8) is the first step of photodissociation, then CH_3 radical will be in the "hot" state whereas the probability of CH_3Cl radical in the "hot" state is less. Photolysis in presence of nitrogen should not strongly favour the products arising from "hot" radicals over those arising from cold radicals. The probability of recombination of CH_3 and CH_2Cl radicals increases. At 9.32 cm Hg and higher pressure of methyl chloride, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$ was also formed. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$ and C_2H_6 were among the products when photolysis were done in presence of hydrogen and nitrogen. According to the radical mechanism their formation may be shown as follows :

At higher temperature the quantum yield of the photolysis increases slightly.

The experimental results presented here support an initial carbon ... chlorine bond cleavage and is

in the line with the view of Mulliken¹ that the continuous absorption band of CH_3Cl is due to the excitation of an electron from a non-bonding orbital on the chlorine atom to a sigma carbon ... chlorine anti-bonding orbital.

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References

1. R. S. MULLIKEN, *Phys. Rev.*, 1935, **47**, 413.
2. HIROSHI YSUBOMURA, KATSUMI KIMURA, KOJI KAYA, JIRO TANAKA and SABURO NAGAKURE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1964, **37**, 417.
3. R. D. SCHULTZ and H. A. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 194.
4. F. P. HUDSON, R. R. WILLIAMS, JR. and W. H. HAMIL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **21**, 1894.
5. R. B. MARTIN and W. A. NOYES, JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4183.
6. G. M. HARRIS and J. E. WILLARD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4678.
7. R. F. PATTIE, W. H. HAMIL and R. R. WILLIAMS, JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **80**, 4224.
8. C. D. BASS and G. C. PIMENTEL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3754.
9. R. F. C. CLARIDGE and J. E. WILLARD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 4992.
10. R. E. ROBERT and P. AUSLOOS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 306.
11. D. G. HILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 32.
12. G. P. SEMELUK and I. UNGER, *Nature*, 1963, **198**, 853.
13. I. UNGER and G. P. SEMELUK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 1427.
14. A. K. BASAK, G. P. SEMELUK and I. UNGER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 1337.
15. A. E. SHILOV and R. D. SABIROVA, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1959, **33**, 1365.
16. K. A. HOLBROOK, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, **57**, 2151.
17. W. FROST and P. ST. LAURENT, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1965, **43**, 3052.
18. E. O. WIGG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 827.
19. E. O. WIGG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 1559.
20. J. A. BELL, *Progress in Physical Organic Chemistry*, Vol. 2, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1964, p. 1.
21. W. B. DEMORE and S. W. BENSON, *Advances in photochemistry*, Vol. 2, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1964, p. 219.